

The role of Media language as a subject in teaching students

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Annotation. This article illustrates that a scientific research is carried out about the importance of teaching the language of the media language as a subject to students, and general research results about its importance, relevance to the professional direction, its purpose, the importance of using methods during the teaching, as well as, general summaries and results are given.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Matbuot tilining fan sifatida talabalarga o'qitilishining qanchalik ahamiyatli ekanligi haqida ilmiy izlanish olib boriladi va uning ahamiyati, kasbiy yo'nalishga aloqadorligi, maqsadi, o'qitish davomida qanday usullardan foydalanish muhimligi haqida umumiy izlanish natijalari va xulosalar beriladi.

Абстрактный. В данной статье проведено научное исследование о важности преподавания языка прессы как предмета студентам, а также приведены общие результаты исследования о его важности в соответствии профессиональному направлению его цели, важности использования методов в процессе обучения и даны выводы.

Key words: daily, shaping, awareness, published, television, radio, internet, newspapers, magazines,

I. Introduction.

Mass media plays crucial role in shaping our daily lives, and influence our opinion, horizon, beliefs, our behavior in some way. This subject highlights how various forms of mass media that affect us and the surround, structures of newspaper and journals, as well as, the importance and the history of television, radio, book, internet, newspapers and magazines. Moreover, it is significant part in shaping awareness of public, spreading news, enhancing cultural norms and values,

entertainment , communicate, understanding media. Since students started learning this subject , they have been acquiring about general and so many specific information related to the different range of mass media types. For instance , how to published books, and their structure , who utilize them ,where are

them sold, and what types of them . Furthermore , it is known that what kinds of language styles are used in where depending on the context, audience and purpose of the communication .

II. Methods.

There are various methods that can be used to teach media languages, depending on the specific goals and objectives of the course. For example,

1) Lecture based instruction – this is traditional method and include delivering information to students through lectures and lessons. This can be beneficial for understanding the media languages.

2) Group discussions-- it can be assistance them by sharing ideas, opinions to their peers and teams, as well as, explaining information widely.

3) Multimedia presentations – utilizing multimedia materials, tools such as, presentations, videos, images, online sites, apps and online educational games. Moreover, playing interactive games in the classrooms with students can encourage them attend the lessons actively.

4) Field trips-- gathering, visiting media production facilities, studios, or museums may give students overwhelming looking at how media languages and styles are used in different contexts.

III. Researching results.

The research summaries illustrate that the purpose of this subject the oral and written forms of the language within the framework of the professional direction, to develop their social and cultural communication skills, in particular to enhance the functional forms and styles of the studied foreign language , practical and theoretical

knowledge of the language , and to freely use the acquired knowledge , skills in professional and scientific activities is to ensure that they can use it. The use of media on a large scale is assumed in the science of press language. These mainly include newspapers, magazines , mass media created and published in a foreign language , and opportunities to use Internet materials. In press language classes, the student should be able to interpret various types of newspaper and magazine materials in English language . Students should be able to know and interpret different articles on a particular topic , the latest news and events happening in the world , articles with theoretical political articles and contents. At

the same time, one should be able to freely translate and study any articles read in one's native language from newspapers and magazines into foreign languages.

After reading and studying Media language , students will learn:

1) Complete and understandable delivery of press texts with the content of the information provided in the original text

2) to be able to use and understand the combination sand concepts used in different contexts in different areas of society

3) to study only the specific aspects when faced with information specific to different cultures encountered in different media

4) to study and analyze texts in the media

5) learns to distinguish text types, to utilize them instead

IV. Conclusion.

The study of media linguistics provides valuable insights into the ways language shapes and is shaped by media messages , helping us better understand the complex relationship between language and media. The study object and methods of the media language course , its place among other linguistic sciences, today's types of press, analysis of information sources such as books, newspapers,

magazines, radio, television, and the Internet, the original meaning of TV programs , convenient and correct ways to find information should know.

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